

IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF MANAGING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF REGIONAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the ongoing work on improving the competitiveness management mechanisms of regional higher education institutions and their relevance. Today, whether it is easier to get into higher education or vice versa, whether higher education is paying off or not, how important are the changes in higher education, the opportunities that are being created, and the competition in the field of education in general about the occupation of rin is explained through this article.

Key words: HEMIS system, competition, higher education, correspondence education, distance education.

INTRODUCTION

After graduation, a great life path begins for a person. On the one hand, the role of higher education in acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills for a person (then referred to as a student or staff) in this life path is incomparable. But today, all higher education It is also a key issue whether educational institutions can provide students with the necessary knowledge and skills.

Training of highly qualified competitive personnel is the most important issue in higher education. Well, first of all, what is required for this? Studying is not just about coming to study and sitting in class. You must test the acquired knowledge somewhere or talk to someone and strengthen it. The main necessary for development. The thing is that it is a competition. When there is a competition, I have to pass it, thinking that I have to pass it, I don't even know how I acquired the knowledge and skills. My personal opinion is that the most important thing in this education is definitely a good teacher. in fact, there is nothing wrong with the teacher, after all, the teachers share all the knowledge and experiences they have and it is a competitive environment.[1]

Of course, getting a job somewhere after graduation is also an important issue. If employers see enough skills in the staff, they will certainly give a job, and it may be the other way around. Well, what is the reason for this in higher education or the staff itself?

In our opinion, if one student's fellow student can get a job, but another cannot, then the reason for this is that the student himself did not acquire enough knowledge, and on the one hand, the higher education institution where he received his education could not create the necessary competitive environment. Because not all students are equally devoted to learning. Maybe there is some problem or something else, but I think that the task of higher education is to make students more interested in studying by creating all the necessary competitive environment for students. But if this situation is observed even then, it means

that the student has no desire and interest, he can trust his father or mother, but one day when his head hits the wall, he will regret thinking about it.

Today, there is a saying that has settled in our minds that it is not necessary to study in higher education in order to find a good job and find your way in life. It is true that a person gets everything he needs in life because of life's trials and difficulties. he can achieve better results than a person with higher education. But why does he need higher education? You can say that everyone will find their own way. It is definitely different. After all, not everyone became successful without studying. It happens one in a million, surely those who work on themselves will achieve such a result.[2]

But today, many young people think that it is not important to study. We are witnessing that most of them are working as emigrants, that is, they just sit at home and wait for success to knock on their doors, maybe they would have achieved better results if they tried. But there are also students who are hungry for good knowledge. They will definitely succeed if they continue like this, after all, the key to success is action, persistence and patience!

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

HEMIS (higher education management information system) information system provides electronic education services to administrative staff, professors and students due to the automation of the main activities of higher education institutions. The information system acts as an information bridge between higher education institutions and the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, and serves to drastically reduce the number of different types of information received from higher education institutions, abandon their paper form, and digitize the management system. [3] Hemis system in our education system. gave many comforts and opportunities.

Higher education is carried out by higher educational institutions by providing scientific and theoretical knowledge and forming specific skills to people who want to become highly qualified specialists in various fields of national economy, science and culture and who have completed the relevant requirements. .[4]

In the process of higher education, the student is given higher education. The concept of higher education means a set of knowledge and skills at a level that allows an independent solution of theoretical and practical problems faced by a specialist in a particular specialty.

Higher education has a long history, which began in Qad. It appeared in Eastern countries. In countries like Egypt, Babylon, and China, a system of higher education was born a few thousand years ago. In high schools, students studied the works of scientists about the laws of development of nature and society, ways of managing the state. Thinkers such as Plato (428-348 BC), Aristotle (384-322 BC) justified the fact that the physical and mental capabilities of each person are fully manifested in 3-level education. That is why Greece and Qad. In Rome, the need for the third - higher stage of education for free people and children of nobles was recognized. Philosophy, philology, music, oratory, medicine, mathematics in ancient higher education. special attention is paid to learning the sciences.[5]

As in many countries of the Muslim East, the first higher education in Turkestan was provided by madrassas. Madrasahs played a decisive role in the emergence of the Muslim Renaissance in the history of mankind.

In the Western countries, the first forms of the higher education system in the modern sense began to appear in the XI - XII centuries. During the renaissance, great scientific discoveries in fields such as mathematics, mechanics, astronomy, navigation, and medicine led

to the deepening of the content and expansion of the scope of higher education. Higher education also progressed in proportion to the development of science, technology, culture and art.[6]

Higher education in the current sense was provided to local residents of Uzbekistan under the leadership of Munavvarqori, the founder of the Central Asian Jadidist movement, at the People's School, which was established in Tashkent on May 12, 1918. Although the network of higher education expanded somewhat during the period of the Soviets, the training of highly educated personnel from the local population was not in a stable position.[7]

After Uzbekistan gained independence, higher education began to develop rapidly. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", higher education is based on the basis of secondary special or vocational education and has two stages - bachelor's and master's. Until a certain period of the implementation of the national personnel training program, higher education is also carried out on the basis of eleven years of general secondary education. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which practices freedom of belief, there are also secular higher education institutions and higher religious education institutions. Higher education in Uzbekistan is under the control of the state. University higher education has a priority status in the country.

State standards of education, curricula are of decisive importance in this. Subjects that are compulsory and theoretical to be studied in them, specialization courses, their training order, amount, time, the ratio between theoretical and practical education, theoretical training, training and production practices, rating period, vacation, bachelor's qualification work, master's theses defense the term is determined in the main pedagogical document - the curriculum. Subjects studied in the curriculum are divided into such parts as humanitarian and socio-economic, mathematical and natural-scientific, general professional, specialized subjects and additional types of education. Subjects in the curriculum are expected to be conducted in compulsory, special, elective and optional forms.[8]

DISCUSSION

Extramural education is a form of obtaining higher and secondary special education without separation from production. It differs from full-time education in that students study independently. External education as a form of obtaining information in a specific field was introduced at the end of the 19th century in Germany, the USA, Great Britain and other countries, and they were initially focused on obtaining technical, military and pedagogical information in the form of an externship, as well as learning literacy. In the 20s of the 20th century, external education courses, later departments, and their current forms appeared in higher education institutions.[9]

External education in Uzbekistan was established in 1938. In the same year, a correspondence department was established at the University of Central Asia. Currently, extramural education is carried out in special centers, departments and units established in special secondary and higher educational institutions. In it, the main part of education is based on independent learning of 60-70% of students, they listen to lectures on academic subjects twice a year in the form of full-time education and pass exams by semesters.[10]

Correspondence education in secondary specialized and higher educational institutions is carried out in correspondence faculty departments of secondary specialized and higher educational institutions. Textbooks and programs are usually common in full-time

and part-time education. The subject-course system of education has been adopted in external higher and secondary special educational institutions. The content of the part-time education system, mandatory minimum levels of knowledge acquired by students, as well as entrance exams are the same as the form of full-time education. Diplomas of the same model are issued for specialists who have graduated from part-time and full-time departments of education. In external education, agriculture, economics, communication and especially ped. training of the most specialists has been launched. The form of extramural education is not used in the training of specialists for the health care system.

Those who graduated from vocational colleges, academic lyceums and general secondary schools are admitted to higher educational institutions regardless of their age. In Uzbekistan, since the 2000-2001 academic year, a special form of external education has been introduced, to which pedagogues with secondary special education and 3 years of work experience are accepted in appropriate directions. For those studying by correspondence in secondary specialized and higher educational institutions, benefits from their main workplaces are provided in the prescribed manner. In Uzbekistan, forms of extramural education, such as televised educational programs, television olympiads, and general secondary education are used in some subjects. In the 2002-2003 academic year, 61,000 students and 73,700 students in secondary special educational institutions studied by correspondence in 45 higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan. External education existed in Uzbekistan in the general secondary education system until 1998, and in the postgraduate system until 2002.[11]

Of course, if a student of a university succeeds through students, that is, by providing good education through a quality and competitive environment, it is certainly a great benefit for the university. even those who mentioned above do not have the desire to study. The reason is that their education system is completely different and the competitive environment is difficult to describe. he may not study the subjects he considers. The competitive environment is very different, every student learns their knowledge skills from each other and is always trying to outdo each other. That is why many famous scientists, businessmen, and billionaires of the world have studied in such universities, and this has brought their reputation to the highest level.

Cadre is derived from the French language, cadre means personnel, and is the basic structure of qualified employees in enterprises, institutions, firms, joint-stock companies, banks, trade unions and public organizations.

After independence, personnel training in Uzbekistan is carried out on the basis of the national personnel training program adopted by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997, and is carried out in a continuous system. Preparation for the stage of formation of a person as a staff is carried out in general secondary schools, academic lyceums. the main contingent of personnel is trained through vocational college, bachelor's and master's degrees. Training of high-scientific, qualified personnel is carried out in post-graduate, residency, adjunct, and doctoral programs. Special attention is paid to the training of highly qualified personnel in the country.

CONCLUSION

As we mentioned earlier, competition is a multifaceted concept, and it is divided into different categories according to the quality, aesthetic, and commercial characteristics of a certain market or product. We can also see it at the level of higher education, and this is an important issue Unfortunately, it is a fact that today the number of people enrolled in higher

education is decreasing year by year. According to statistics: 1 million 193 thousand 169 applicants in 2020, 948 thousand 211 in 2021, 1 million 214 thousand 232 in 2022, 1 million 18 thousand applicants in 2023. You can see that it is decreasing year by year. This is one of the main reasons. today, there are a lot of activities of tour companies that apply for study abroad, and there you will study for 1 year, learn a language and become a student of foreign universities.

References:

1. I. Tishabayeva, Z. Xatamova, N. Ibragimov, O. Xamdanova. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON TARIXI FANLARINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION, 1(7). Retrieved from <http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/690>
2. Кочкорова Г. Д. ВЫСШЕЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ В РАМКАХ КОНЦЕПЦИИ «УНИВЕРСИТЕТ 3.0» ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА «УНИВЕРСИТЕТ 3.0» КОНСЕПСИЯСИ ДОИРАСИДА ОЛИЙ ТАЛИМ // HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE CONCEPT // Таълим тизимида ижтимоий-гуманитар фанлар. – 2021. – С. 16.
3. Кочкорова Г. Д. золотой век исламского возрождения // Европейский журнал гуманитарных наук и достижений в области образования. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 127-129.
4. Кочкорова Г. Д. Роль негосударственных некоммерческих организаций в формировании нравственных устоев гражданского общества // Т.-2008. – 2008.
5. Xamdanova O.M., Xatamova Z.N., Ibragimov N., Tishabaeva I. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIMIDA UZVIY BOG'LIQLIK VA RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION, 1(7). Retrieved from <http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/689>
6. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ СИСТЕМЫ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗАХ ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИХ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1091>
7. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). РОЛЬ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1116>
8. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). СТРАТЕГИИ МАРКЕТИНГА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1069>
9. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1068>

10.Ibragimov Navro'zbek Kimsanbaevich (2023). THE ISSUE OF EMPLOYMENT FOR GRADUATES IN IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF COMPETITIVENESS OF REGIONAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8415277>

11.Kochkorova , G. , Irmatova , D. , & Abdurasulova, D. . (2023). ASSOCIATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY INTO HUMAN CONSCIOUSNESS. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(10), 326–329. Retrieved from <https://www.researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/2858>

